

Proposal Narrative

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

Creating a captivating and cohesive narrative that highlights the relevance of your project, conveys a clear structure, and provides transparent goals and deliverables.

Benefits

A cohesive proposal narrative does not appear out of nowhere. Especially not in MAA context when the needs of end-users need to be put central, but they are hard to reach and have limited capacity to contribute. These tools can help optimize the use of everyone's limited time.

Practical recommendations

A good proposal narrative:

- Contains a clear problem statement and challenge
- Is transparent in what it will solve, where it's boundaries are
- And is tailored to the target audience

Clear Problem Statement

While a core challenge is often outlined in a Call for Proposals, actually defining and describing the challenge is left to the consortium. Especially relevant in MAA, since it is your job as a consortium to pick a specific challenge that is significant to the end-users outlined in the call. Defining and describing a clear problem statement is not only vital to convince evaluators, but it also helps clarify your goals towards potential new partners you may want to on-board. Start by doing a [Causes and Effects](#) or [Problem Tree](#) exercise to clarify your problem statement.

Once the central problem is clear you build your narrative and give it body by considering what the impact is of that central problem across different societal dimensions. Use tools like [PEST Analysis](#) to help co-create the full scope of your argument. If a desired future has been outlined you can also employ [Backcasting](#) to help define build a [strong strategy](#), and collect them in a [narrative canvas](#).

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Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Transparent communication about agenda's, expectations, and results

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)*

[Persona's](#)

[PEST Analysis](#)

[Backcasting](#)

[Sphere of Influence](#)

[Into The Graph: Feasibility versus](#)

[Usefulness](#)

[Causes and Effects](#)

[Problem Tree](#)

[Guide to SSH](#)

[Reflective Tool](#)

[Strong Strategy](#)

[Narrative Canvas](#)

[Proposal Evaluation](#)

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Transparent Boundaries

Calls tend to contain ambiguous, vague, and open to interpretation statements. Partly this is on purpose, to give participants degrees of freedom in designing the best project proposals. It is, however, impossible to everything. You will need to define a clear scope on what you and your consortium will be addressing, and what you won't be addressing. There are several co-creative exercises that can help you in establishing transparent boundaries, such as the [Sphere of Influence](#) which helps establish what is inherently in- and outside of your control. If you still have too many activities left to be feasible it can help to do an Into The Graph exercise on [Feasibility versus Usefulness](#).

Target Audience

For a true multi-actor approach proposal the project needs to revolve around a challenge which is currently being face by your end-users. Evaluators will be on the look-out for the beneficiaries of your proposal, and whether those overlap with your end-users. In practice defining clear end-users might in fact be tricky. To help evaluators understand your target audience it can be helpful to borrow a marketing technique and create [Persona's](#).

Additional Noteworthy Mentions:

- In the call there may also be a request to include the social sciences and humanities(SSH). Check out this [Guide to SSH](#) resource to weave that into your narrative.
- The "Communities of Practice Playbook" holds a chapter on developing a Vision.
- EIT Climate-KIC use The Pentagonal Problem to help define the problem statement.
- The Mini Campaign Design Challenge from Co-creation Lab is a neat way to explore engagement strategies towards your target audience(s).

Evaluation

Ready with your narrative? Once you have drafted the first version it is smart to read through it through the eyes of an evaluator. Check out our guide on Proposal Evaluation for extensive reflection on the narrative. In a hurry? Use this [Reflective Tool](#) instead.

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